

THE ESSENCE OF THE MODULE SYSTEM OF TRAINING.

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ANNOTATION: *In the article, the use of integrative and innovative methods to facilitate the pedagogical outlook of lower (1-2) year students in higher education institutions and to further expand their thinking, to strengthen their knowledge, and to facilitate their learning skills, and to apply them in practice. instructions are given.*

Key words: *integrative, innovative, module, pedagogy, innovative, student, process, method, education, pedagogue, upbringing, person.*

Introduction

The term "modular learning" is an international concept related to module, which means a node consisting of interrelated elements that can perform a single function. In this sense, it is understood as a complete block of information, as the main means of teaching the module [1].

A module covers the fundamental concepts of a discipline – a particular phenomenon or law, or a section, or a particular larger topic or group of interrelated concepts.

A module is a logically completed unit of educational material, aimed at learning one or more fundamental concepts of a subject.

Modular training is considered one of the most stable systems of training, because it is best adapted to the learning system of the human brain. The basis of the module's teaching is based on the organization of the human brain tissue module.

The tissue of the human brain consists of about 15 billion neurons (nerve cells) or conditional modules. Tissue cells are in numerous collisions with each other. The number of collisions of one cell and its tumor with another cell and its tumor reaches 6000.

Therefore, the number of collisions (contacts) in the brain tissue is an astronomical number (15000000000×6000). From this point of view, the module is considered as a cell of the learning process.

At the same time, this cell is composed of various elements that have a unique integrity and structure to the informational totality.

The modular system of teaching was officially discussed for the first time in 1972, at the World Conference of UNESCO in Tokyo. The module teaching technology is derived from the general theory of functional systems, neurophysiology of thinking, pedagogic psychology.

Research methodology

According to research in these areas, the human brain is a tissue module that best receives information in quantum form (in other words, in the form of specific portions).

Usually, the module consists of 3-6 hours of lectures and related Practical (seminar) and laboratory exercises.

Based on a strict systematic (multifaceted) analysis of the explanatory apparatus of science, the most effective module is created. This makes it possible to separate the group of fundamental expressions, to logically and compactly grow the material. Since the module is an independent structural unit, in some cases, students are given the opportunity to listen to only a number of modules, not the whole subject. This creates an opportunity to optimally plan the individual and independent work of talented students.

In module training, the possibility of training differentiation is created by the Full, reduced and in-depth classification of educational programs. That is, it will be possible to individualize teaching.

The following goals are aimed at the transition to teaching the module:

- ensuring the continuity of teaching (between subjects and within the subject);
- individualization of teaching;
- creating sufficient conditions for independent learning of educational material;
- acceleration of training;
- achieving effective mastery of science.

Thus, in teaching the module, full necessary conditions are created for students to learn according to their abilities.

The effectiveness of the transition to the module system of education depends on the following factors:

The level of the educational institution's material and technical base;

- qualification level of teaching staff;
- level of preparation of students;
- evaluation of intended results;
- development of didactic materials;
- analysis of results and optimization of modules.

The following materials are prepared for each module:

- tests to monitor students' knowledge;
- tasks for individual work;
- assignments for independent work;
- educational methodological handouts;
- list of educational and scientific literature;

- working curriculum.

For each module, a set of handouts and visual materials will be prepared and given to the student before the session.

The module comes with recommended literature. Each student moves from one module to another as he learns the material. Gifted students can pass tests without depending on others.

Modular teaching requires the delivery of problem-based and guided lectures that provide generalized information on the main issues of the subject. Lectures should focus on the development of students' creative abilities.

Practical and laboratory exercises of the module are created together with lectures, which are supplemented with new material to study the content of the lectures. Students will acquire some practical skills.

When preparing the text of lectures, it is appropriate to use the methods of structuring and systematization, and to present the materials in the form of a block diagram, a block of pictures. In this case, the efficiency of material absorption increases, because:

- the final purpose of the module is understood;
- the connections between the elements of the educational material and its transitions are clearly indicated;
- the main aspects are highlighted;
- the entire volume of the educational material (module) is embodied before the eyes of the student.

When structuring the content of the educational material in the module system, first of all, the task of "compressing" information is intended.

It is necessary to try to provide knowledge in a complete, easy-to-use manner.

The most solid mastery is achieved when educational information is transmitted simultaneously in 4 different ways - pictorial, numerical, symbolic and verbal.

This situation serves as a basis for creating a modular educational methodology. For each module, it is appropriate to place symbolic signs (in the form of questions), depict questions in the form of pictures, present formulas, tables, graphs and methodological instructions [2, 3].

Block of pictures, block of diagrams and other pictorial (visual) materials also serve as handouts for students. In addition, it would be appropriate to create an explanatory dictionary of terms for each subject, including the module.

Conclusions and suggestions

In order to increase the effectiveness of teaching the module, it is necessary to use the following methods of teaching: - brainstorming, problem dialogues, heuristic conversations, educational games, etc.

The content of the module system of education shows its following advantages:

- provision of continuity of education between disciplines, modules within disciplines;
- establishment of methodically based compatibility of all types of educational process within each module and between them;
- adaptability of the structure of the module structure of the science;
- regular and effective monitoring of students' learning (after each module);
- classification of students according to their immediate ability (after the initial modules, the teacher may recommend individual mastery of the subject to some students);
- as a result of "compressing" information, acceleration of studies, effective use of classroom hours and optimization of the structure of study time, lectures, practical (experimental) classes, individual and independent work.

As a result, the student will have sufficient knowledge, skills and training.

Thus, using module training, training of a qualified specialist is provided on the basis of:

- continuity of education (in which the efficiency of mastering subjects increases);

- acceleration of training (as a result, most of the information is acquired through computer networks during individual and independent work;

- individualization of studies (the student will have the opportunity to learn according to his abilities).

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